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RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Framework for RF-EMF Time Series Analysis Through Multi-Scale Time Averaging

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ABSTRACT Five European systems for continuous monitoring of outside radio-frequency (RF) electromagnetic field (EMF) provide important insights into the long-term in situ variability of RF-EMF, as a valuable feature for accessing RF-EMF in areas with increased sensitivity to EMF exposure. Unfortunately, their current presentation of field variability through a simple timeline is not suitable for a comprehensive insight into RF-EMF behavior, especially not for applications where annual comparison of field levels over a certain period of time is required. Driven by the need to overview monitored data in some distinctive way and further examine hidden phenomena embedded in system's EMF data series, this paper presents an additional method for analyzing RF-EMF time series through multi-scale time averaging. A case study was selected to demonstrate the time-averaging framework, using a five-year RF-EMF dataset obtained from a sensor, installed on the campus of the University of Novi Sad, as part of the Serbian EMF RATEL monitoring network. Although this case study reveals some site-specific details, such as a daily ratio between maximum and minimum field levels of 3.6 for weekdays and 2.1 for weekends, the time-averaging framework is applicable to any monitoring network. Furthermore, it is designed to present its findings in a simple manner and to be affirmative of the general population's perception on unavoidable presence of RF-EMF in the environment, while ultimately contributing to a more rational understanding of the potential impact of everyday RF-EMF on their health.

INDEX TERMS EMF monitoring, wireless sensor network, data analysis, temporal variability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Man-made electromagnetic fields (EMFs) have been used over time as an efficient and cost-effective carrier for data transmission in telecommunications and have become a key component for widespread wireless technologies. Since the use of EMFs means broadcasting through the air, the radio-frequency (RF) EMFs are inevitably present, at all times, in the human environment.

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Furthermore, the proliferation of various sources of RF-EMF increases the intensity of the fields in surroundings, especially with the advent of new wireless services, which is consistently accompanied by additional public concerns about the impact of these fields on human health [1].

To alleviate this concern and gain a broad overview of actual field levels and corresponding exposures, large-scale measurement campaigns have been conducted worldwide, investigating public exposure to a number of technologies [2], [3], [4], [5], in different environments [6], [7], [8], [9], [10],

FIGURE 1. Concept of the EMF RATEL monitoring network [19].

FIGURE 2. Growth of the EMF RATEL network [19].

and both in the low- [11], [12], [13] and high-frequency bands [2], [3], [4], [5].

Most of these studies have relied on conventional on-site measurements in spot, both for indoor and outdoor settings. However, a subset has adopted progressive methodologies such as drone measurements [14], drive tests [15], [16], [17], and modern EMF monitoring networks [10], [18] including the most recent monitoring system in the Republic of Serbia – EMF RATEL [19].

A key advantage of these new approaches is that, unlike spot measurements, RF-EMF levels can be easily measured over a wide area, providing information on the spatial and temporal distribution of the field. However, in the general interest of the public, all acquired field results must be used to test compliance with prescribed reference levels, derived from established international guidelines [20], [21], [22].

In line with this fact, human exposure to EMF remains one of the fundamental issues for the scientific community [23]. Therefore, any new information and knowledge about EMF, in general, and the consequent exposure [24], can be significant for a quantitative understanding of the presence of EMF in the environment, and are especially valuable in the case of new wireless technologies established on EMF [25] and their interaction/effects on human tissue, whether they are adverse [26], [27] or beneficial [28].

Searching for such new EMF information, several studies emerge reviewing: used measuring technologies [29], from spot measurements to the mixed methodologies, along with their improvements [30], [31]; continuous observation and results from the leading EMF monitoring networks [10], as a most relevant to this work; and approaches for processing EMF data to extract hidden phenomena [32], [33], [34], selected from a wider set of data mining technologies [35], with the aim of much better assessing the quantification of RF-EMF exposure and compliance with internationally established safety limits [20], [21], [22], as well as national EMF legislation.

Currently, five EMF monitoring networks are operable in Europe: NOEF – Greece [36], SMRF – Catalonia (Spain) [37], Observatoire des Ondes – France-Belgium [38], the ANCOM – Romania [39] and EMF RATEL – Serbia [19]. However, there are/were some other similar networks [40].

Unfortunately, some were in the form of a pilot project, not available anymore, while others have low visibility without open access to their measurement results.

As the number of such networks is expected to increase in the future, the processing of their RF-EMF data and the extraction of new field features, especially from long-term monitoring process, gained substantial attention [41], [42], [43]. In this paper, the recent use of time averaging approach to extract hidden characteristics from RF-EMF monitoring in kindergartens/schools [43], is extended to the framework of additional analyses that can cover any period, with the aim of comparing annual field levels for a better understanding of the real-life RF-EMF.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the essentials of EMF RATEL and the EMF condition of a case study location. The theoretical foundation for the proposed time-averaging framework is discussed in Section III, while Section IV presents outcomes of the performed EMF analyses and discussion. At the end, Section V reviews the main results and considers further research.

II. EMF RATEL AND EMF MICRO-ENVIRONMENT

The EMF RATEL network was established in 2017 thanks to the vision of the Serbian Regulatory Authority for Electronic Communications and Postal Services (RATEL). It is based on autonomous EMF sensors, territorially distributed and linked in a wireless network, as conceptually shown in Fig. 1 [19].

The EMF RATEL system is gradually growing every year with the installation of new EMF sensors, as shown in Fig. 2. Currently, 116 sensors are used to cover the major cities in Serbia, as illustrated in Fig. 3, with their number within each city correlating with the population density of the city.

Considering the type of sensor location, 55% of them have been installed in schools/kindergartens, as shown in Fig. 4.

The overall number of measurement results in EMF RATEL database has reached 46 million, with the distribution of sensor measurements shown in Fig. 5, ranging from 145200 samples to 641280. Given such a large number of results, especially per sensor, the usual presentation of field levels on a timeline, shown in Fig. 6, had to be limited, as was done in the EMF RATEL system for a period of 240 days.

Unfortunately, this was necessary for the efficient operation of the system portal; however, it exposes the fact that only

FIGURE 3. The EMF RATEL coverage of the Serbian territory [19].

FIGURE 4. Distribution of EMF sensors [43].

FIGURE 5. Distribution of acquired results.

a portion of the available information on RF-EMF variability is offered to users and thus additional comprehensive insight into the behavior of field is required. Consequently, this detail was the main motivation for establishing a time-averaging methodology with the intention of providing a simple, user-friendly insight into the acquired monitoring results [43].

A. EMF SENSOR SAMPLING

The sensors in EMF RATEL are installed at fixed locations and perform broadband and isotropic RF-EMF monitoring

in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 7 GHz [19]. The sensors are compliant with ITU-T Recommendation K.83 [44] and use six-minute averaging during monitoring process, as required by EN 50413:2020 standard [45] and its Serbian counterpart SRPS EN 50413:2020, regulating the RF-EMF measurements and assessment of the human exposure to this field.

The sensor’s internal averaging of samples over a period of six minutes [45] is shown in Fig. 7, and it is established on the scientific findings about the time required for the absorption of RF-EMF energy in human tissue [20]. Consequently, this was the decisive point for continuing the averaging within the proposed time-averaging framework in this paper and [43].

Fig. 7 shows that 240 field outputs per day per sensor are provided ($(24^{\text{hours}} \times 60^{\text{minutes}}) / 6^{\text{minutes}} = 240$). Accordingly, one of the earliest installed EMF RATEL sensors collects data for 2672 days, while the distribution of acquisition days in the EMF RATEL monitoring process is given in Fig. 8, ranging from 605 days to 2672. Also, the number of measurements per sensor is given in Fig. 9, where sensors are sorted from earliest installed to the newest one on the diagram abscissa.

However, it can be expected that during the lifetime of EMF RATEL the overall number of measurements and acquisition days will increase even more, which again indicates that the modest timeline presentation will not be so informative in the future. Therefore, a new approach to displaying EMF results is welcome, which was an additional motivation for the time-averaging framework in this paper and [43].

Regarding the monitoring process, the daily acquired results are initially stored in the internal memory of the sensor and are transferred once a day to the system database [19], using the existing mobile telephony infrastructure.

B. EMF CONDITIONS ON THE UNIVERSITY CAMPUS

The campus of the University of Novi Sad (UNS) is located in the southwestern part of the city of Novi Sad and is one of the largest campuses in Serbia. It is visited by 50,000 students and 5,000 university personnel every day. A population of this size requires an extensive coverage by the mobile telephony signal, which is provided by three national operators and their base stations (BSs), as shown in Fig. 10.

Three BSs are installed within the campus (BS3, BS4 and BS5), while two additional ones are located in its vicinity (BS1 and BS2). They provide current 2G/3G/4G services, radiating RF fields into the campus, where their emission is shown by the radiation patterns depicted in Fig. 10. In addition, there is expectation that 5G service will start in the near future, which will further increase field levels on campus.

In this simple overview, the colors identify the mobile technology installed on the BS: yellow refers to 2G (GSM), light purple to 3G (UMTS), and light blue to 4G (LTE) for telecom operator A1 [46], while blue, purple, and yellow represent 2G, 3G, and 4G, respectively, for two additional operators Yettel [47] and MTS [48].

FIGURE 6. Dissemination of EMF RATEL monitoring results [19].

FIGURE 7. EMF sensor’s internal averaging of measurement samples.

FIGURE 8. Distribution of acquisition days.

FIGURE 9. Number of results per sensor.

In connection with the necessity of complete identification of EMF conditions on campus, as well as the understanding of operators for this research, the relevant radiation parameters of BSs are shown in Tables 1-3, as agreed by the operator for publication.

C. EMF MONITORING ON THE UNIVERSITY CAMPUS

The UNS campus area is monitored by two EMF sensors: S1 [49] and S2 [50], installed at the locations marked with orange stars in Fig. 10. For this study, sensor S1 installed on the roof of the kindergarten “Radosno detinjstvo – Veseli vrtic” [51]

was chosen to demonstrate the proposed framework of time averaging on multiple scales. The main reason is the position of BS3, which is located in front of this kindergarten, at a distance of only 70 m, as shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 [51]. Such a short distance causes great public concerns and thus the EMF monitoring of S1 is of particular importance.

Furthermore, the BS3 antennas are located at a height of 12 m above the ground, as can be seen in Fig. 13, which is an unusually low installation height, especially considering the public’s perception of RF-EMF and the fact that children are

TABLE 1. BS technical radiation parameters – Yettel operator [47].

Technology	BS	TRX	Azimuth [°]				Mechanical down-tilt [°]				Electrical down-tilt [°]				Antennas
			Sector				Sector				Sector				
			1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	
GSM 900	BS 1	4+4+4	45	200	290	-	4	1	4	-	2	2	2	-	Kathrein 739495
GSM 1800		4+4+4									2	2	2	-	
UMTS 900		1+1+1									4	2	6	-	
UMTS 2100		1+1+1									4	2	6	-	
LTE 800		1+1+1									4	4	2	-	
LTE 1800		1+1+1									4	4	2	-	
LTE 2100		1+1+1									4	4	2	-	

TABLE 2. BS technical radiation parameters – A1 operator [46].

Technology	BS	TRX	Azimuth [°]				Mechanical down-tilt [°]				Electrical down-tilt [°]				Antennas
			Sector				Sector				Sector				
			1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	
GSM 900	BS 1	3+3+3	30	150	260	-	0	0	0	-	7	7	5	-	Huawei AQU4518R6 0v0
UMTS 2100		1+1+1									6	6	6	-	
LTE 800		1+1+1									9	9	10	-	
LTE 1800		1+1+1									6	6	6	-	
LTE 2100		1+1+1									6	6	6	-	

TABLE 3. BS technical radiation parameters - MTS operator [48].

Technology	BS	TRX	Azimuth [°]				Mechanical down-tilt [°]				Electrical down-tilt [°]				Antennas
			Sector				Sector				Sector				
			1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	
UMTS 2100	BS 2	1+1+1	45	210	320	-	0	0	0	-	4	4	6	-	Kathrein 80010864
LTE 800		1+1+1									4	5	7	-	
LTE 1800		1+1+1									4	4	6	-	
LTE 2100		1+1+1									4	4	6	-	
GSM 900	BS 3	4+4+4	70	145	350	-	-2	-2	-2	-	4	4	2	-	Kathrein 80010892
GSM 1800		4+4+4									4	4	2	-	
UMTS 2100		1+1+1									4	2	6	-	
LTE 800		1+1+1									4	4	2	-	
LTE 1800		1+1+1									2	2	2	-	
LTE 2100	1+1+1	2	4	6	-										
GSM 900	BS 4	4+4+4	10	190	310	-	0	0	0	0	8	6	8	-	Kathrein 80010292
UMTS 2100		1+1+1	10	190	250	310					9	5	10	10	
LTE 800		1+1+1	10	190	250	310					9	6	7	8	
LTE 1800		1+1+1	10	190	250	310					8	5	7	7	
LTE 2100		1+1+1	10	190	250	310					9	5	10	10	
UMTS 2100	BS 5	1+1+1	120	190	355	-	10	10	10	-	0	0	0	-	80010711

present in the kindergarten building and its yard every day. Also, the “Jovan Popovic” elementary school is positioned in the adjacent part of the same building, as can be seen in Fig. 14, and also increases the number of children in the vicinity of BS3.

Consequently, the location is considered a highly sensitive EMF micro-environment, within the UNS campus area that has already been agreed as an area of increased sensitivity. Therefore, comprehensive EMF monitoring is required.

Observing the radiation patterns of the BS3 antennas, it can be assumed with great certainty that, by installing the S1 sensor at the position where the patterns from sectors 1 and 2 overlap, the S1 will mostly monitor radiation originating from BS3. Moreover, the relatively short distance between S1 and BS3 (only 70 m) leads to another important fact – BS3 will behave as the dominant RF-EMF source in the vicinity of this location and the S1 sensor itself.

D. SPECTRAL ANALYSIS OF THE SITE

Given the sensitivity of the kindergarten “Radosno detinjstvo – Veseli vrtic”, the campus was visually inspected in 2022 and 2023, in addition to spectral analysis at several locations, to determine existing sources of RF-EMF in this area. The results of spectral analyses for the kindergarten site are presented in Fig. 15 and Fig. 16.

The frequency components of 800 MHz, 900 MHz, 1800 MHz, and 2100 MHz of the electric field (E-field) are central in the spectral content, which corresponds to BS3 parameters from Table 3. The figure shows the presence of an additional contribution at 2700 MHz, which falls within the S1 operating range and is therefore included in the measured field, although no further data were available to trace it to a known source.

Spectral analyses confirmed that MTS BS3 is the dominant EMF source for the field measured by S1 sensor and that this

FIGURE 10. UNS campus area and BS positions.

FIGURE 12. Sensor S1 and MTS BS3 – satellite [51].

FIGURE 13. MTS BS3.

FIGURE 11. Sensor S1 and MTS BS3 – terrain [51].

sensor, in addition to monitoring of BS3 EMF, can indirectly detect the population’s habit of using 2G/3G/4G services.

III. THEORETICAL BASIS OF TIME-AVERAGING

EMF RATEL sensors provide 240 outputs per day, where the sensor dataset can be described as a discrete sequence:

$$E(n), n \in [1, 2, 3 \dots N], \quad (1)$$

where n denotes a discrete time, with one measurements every 6 minutes, and N is the total number of sensor outputs. Since the sequence $E(1), \dots, E(N)$ is a data series of RF-EMF values obtained at consecutive, evenly spaced times, it can be viewed as a EMF time series.

A. DAILY TIME PATTERN

Regarding EMF fluctuation, it is beneficial to gain insight into the diurnal variability, for weekdays and weekends. Such type of analysis can be done using the following equation:

$$\bar{E}_A(m) = \frac{1}{N_m} \sum_{j=0}^{N_m-1} E(m + 240 \cdot j), \quad m \in [1, 2, 3, \dots, 240], \quad (2)$$

where m includes 240 sampling times in a day and N_m is the number of days for averaging. The product $240 \cdot j$ means the summing of instances at the same time position on different days. Separate averaging for weekdays and weekends can be performed if further investigation is needed.

The standard deviation (STD) – $s(m)$ of all samples obtained at each sampling time m is calculated as [52]:

$$s_A(m) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_m - 1} \sum_{j=0}^{N_m-1} [E(m + 240 \cdot j) - \bar{E}_A(m)]^2}, \quad m \in [1, 2, 3, \dots, 240]. \quad (3)$$

FIGURE 14. Location of BS3 next to the kindergarten “Radosno detinjstvo – Veseli vrtić” and the school “Jovan Popovic” – Google satellite view.

B. WEEKLY TIME PATTERN

Analysis of the weekly pattern of RF-EMF can be done using the following equation [43]:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{E}_B(m) &= \frac{1}{N_m} \sum_{j=0}^{N_m-1} E(m + 7 \cdot 240 \cdot j), \quad m \in [1, 2, 3, \dots, 1680], \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where m includes $7 \cdot 240 = 1680$ sampling times in a week. The product “ $7 \cdot 240 \cdot j$ ” means that the sum is over instances simultaneously in different weeks.

The standard deviation STD – $s(m)$ for this averaged field value is calculated as follows [52]:

$$s_B(m) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_m - 1} \sum_{j=0}^{N_m-1} [E(m + 7 \cdot 240 \cdot j) - \bar{E}_B(m)]^2}, \quad m \in [1, 2, 3, \dots, 1680]. \tag{5}$$

C. MONTHLY TIME PATTERN

A further analysis of RF-EMF pattern can be performed for a yearly period using the following equation:

$$\bar{E}_C(m) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{240 \cdot d \cdot (N_m - 1)} \sum_{j=0}^{N_m-1} \sum_{k=0}^{d-1} \sum_{i=0}^{240-1} [E(m + 12 \cdot j + k + i) - \bar{E}_C(m)]^2}, \quad m \in [1, 2, 3, \dots, 12] \tag{7}$$

FIGURE 15. Spectral analysis at the kindergarten in 2022 [51].

$$= \frac{1}{N_m} \sum_{j=0}^{N_m-1} \left[\frac{1}{d} \sum_{k=0}^{d-1} \left[\frac{1}{240} \sum_{i=0}^{240-1} E(m + 12 \cdot j + k + i) \right] \right], \quad m \in [1, 2, 3, \dots, 12], \tag{6}$$

where m covers the twelve months, d is the number of days in month m and i refers to the 240 samples acquired each day. In this case, the standard deviation $s(m)$ is calculated by equation (7), as shown at the bottom of the page, [52].

At the end of this mathematical consideration, it should be emphasized that only some of the potentially interesting EMF analyses using the proposed time-averaging methodology are

FIGURE 16. Spectral analysis at the kindergarten in 2023.

presented in the section, while some others can be initiated and found to be very useful.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

EMF monitoring systems can produce many EMF datasets, which is helpful for various data analyses [10]. The recently introduced decomposition of seasonal trends using LOESS analysis [42] provides some valuable information on trends, seasonal, and noise components in the Greek system – NOEF [36]. Analyzing almost two decades of data, from the end of 2003 until February 2022 [42], the temporal differences are presented in a manner of straight-line of subsequent years. Although, this method is useful for longer periods, it has the limitation of low capability for smaller periods.

On the contrary, time-averaging of EMF time series in EMF monitoring systems, considered in this paper and [43], as an additional methodology for EMF analysis has a different focus – extracting hidden knowledge about the field, within smaller time intervals and specific periods, such as day, week, month and year. The goal is to estimate the typical field behavior in these intervals and later compare them by year.

The proposed framework is illustrated in the case study of the RF-EMF dataset of S1, which is reduced to five years from 2018 to 2022 in order to have a rounded period for analysis.

A. TIME AVERAGING PER DAY

This type of time-averaging analysis provides insight into the daily pattern of E-field, and can be separated for weekdays and weekends, as presented in Fig 17 and Fig. 18.

The E-field levels with their standard deviations is obtained using equations (2) and (3) over the RF-EMF results acquired in 2022. Both figures show the averaged values of the E-field and the upper/lower bounds obtained from $s(m)$. By analyzing the curves, a specific waveform can be observed, with a minimum occurring around 5 a.m. and a maximum around noon, for this case study.

The S1 data is mainly influenced by BS3, which allows the E-field curves to provide insight into the patterns of mobile phone services usage in this specific environment. However, the time pattern provides additional information

FIGURE 17. Averaging over time – per weekdays in 2022.

FIGURE 18. Averaging over time – per weekend in 2022.

about the time of minimal and maximal radiation and the hourly activities of RF-EMF sources.

Both curves show low use of telecom services before dawn, followed by low EMF radiation, while increasing to maximum around noon. This can provide valued information for further EMF investigation in this area, as a specific application of the proposed methodology, which tells when is the most suitable time for EMF measurements, which is especially important for EMF accredited laboratories, as discussed in subsection IV.F.

Furthermore, it can be observed in Fig. 17 that after the field reaches its maximum of 2.2 V/m around noon, it decreases in the afternoon hours because most of the activities on campus take place during working hours, while students leave campus in the afternoon. Therefore, the use of mobile phone services decreases thereafter.

TABLE 4. Dynamics and variability of E-field at the case study location.

Dynamics for working days		Dynamics for weekend days		Variability	
<i>dyn</i> (5 a.m.)	<i>dyn</i> (12 p.m.)	<i>dyn</i> (5 a.m.)	<i>dyn</i> (12 p.m.)	working days	weekend days
0.173 V/m	0.627 V/m	0.148 V/m	0.311 V/m	41.03 %	27.65 %

In contrast, Fig. 18 shows that during the weekend, after the field reaches its maximum of 1.8 V/m around noon, it maintains an almost constant level in the afternoon because there are no students on campus.

Two additional parameters can be defined, the dynamics of the E-field at time m as:

$$dyn(m) = (\bar{E}(m) + s(m)) - (\bar{E}(m) - s(m)) = 2s(m), \quad (8)$$

and the field variability as:

$$var[\%] = \frac{\bar{E}_{max} - \bar{E}_{min}}{\bar{E}_{max}} \cdot 100\%. \quad (9)$$

These can further describe the field behavior, especially the variability, as it smooths over time and the analyzed period, and can provide better insight into the field daily behavior.

Table 4 summarizes the dynamics and variability, for this case study. The maximum dynamics can be observed around noon, while it decreases in the afternoon during weekdays and remains almost constant during weekends, similar to temporal behavior of the E-field.

The ratio of $dyn(12\text{ p.m.})/dyn(5\text{ a.m.})$ on weekdays is 3.6, while on weekends it is 2.1. This information, together with information on the variability, which is about 41% on weekdays vs almost 28% on weekends, provides a key indication of the intensity of mobile telephony use, the resulting RF-EMF and ultimately the exposure, which is of particular interest to the general population living nearby.

B. TIME-AVERAGING PER HOUR FOR THE WEEKDAYS AND WEEKEND – ANNUAL OVERVIEW

The previous analysis was done for the year 2022, making the initial presentation, as simple as possible. However, it can be repeated for many years monitored, as was done for the 2018-2022 range, and shown in Fig. 19 and Fig. 20.

Standard deviations are not included in these figures, yet their values are given in Tables 5 and 6.

Figs. 19 and 20 show that the temporal pattern is similar in different years, although the field strength increased over time. The minimum and maximum are reached at almost the same time for each observed year, which provides information that the activities of the population on campus and the surrounding micro-environment were almost the same from year to year.

However, such hidden details can be valuable for the daily work of laboratories for EMF investigation, as an additional example of the use of time-averaging methodology.

The annual increase in EMF levels cannot be directly seen from the traditional timeline presented in Fig. 6. However, it is valuable for decision makers to have a tool that is able to provide this insight into the behavior of RF-EMF, in relation

FIGURE 19. Averaging over time – per weekdays – 2018-2022.

FIGURE 20. Averaging over time – per weekend – 2018-2022.

to the implementation of any new mobile phone service due to the increased number of people in the environment.

C. TIME-AVERAGING FOR THE WHOLE WEEK

An additional attractive investigation could be the weekly time pattern of field strength, as shown in Fig. 21, for the year 2022, and in Fig. 22, for the period of 2018-2022, using the proposed time averaging defined by (4) and (5).

Fig. 21 shows the E-field variability at each sampling time throughout the week, where the repeatability of the behavior of the E-field can be observed for each day during weekdays and weekends.

TABLE 5. Basic analysis of the E-field and STD over time – for weekdays – 2018-2022.

	2018		2019		2020		2021		2022	
	E [V/m]	STD								
min	0.844	0.101	1.008	0.061	1.081	0.047	1.137	0.075	1.297	0.076
avg	1.074	0.172	1.332	0.168	1.404	0.162	1.588	0.163	1.782	0.196
max	1.261	0.244	1.625	0.288	1.672	0.270	1.948	0.234	2.199	0.316

TABLE 6. Basic analysis of the E-field and STD over time – for weekends – 2018-2022.

	2018		2019		2020		2021		2022	
	E [V/m]	STD								
min	0.848	0.091	1.013	0.061	1.081	0.043	1.155	0.096	1.306	0.074
avg	1.043	0.164	1.204	0.104	1.312	0.110	1.483	0.143	1.622	0.142
max	1.176	0.238	1.329	0.148	1.448	0.177	1.660	0.199	1.806	0.236

FIGURE 21. Averaging over time – per week in 2022.

However, the decrease in the E-field level in the afternoon and evening hours is more pronounced during weekdays than on weekends, when the E-field level is almost constant.

In addition, some further specificities can be observed in Fig. 21, such as the peak intensity that is not the same for each weekday, the duration of intervals around the peak, and many others useful for target groups from subsection IV.F.

It is also interesting to compare the daily E-field levels by year, as shown in Fig. 22. A strong increase in field strength can be observed, confirming that the use of mobile telephony services is increasing in an almost constant manner, which may be important fact for the activities of national agencies for protection against electromagnetic radiation.

Fig. 21 shows only the E-field curves while corresponding standard deviation analyses are given in Table 7.

The presented averaging analysis for the entire week can be further separated for weekdays and weekends, as well as for any period of the week, for example few days, as seen in [43].

Also, using the proposed time-averaging methodology, it is possible to analyze any period longer than a week that may be required/interesting in foreseen EMF applications.

FIGURE 22. Averaging over time – per week – 2018-2022.

D. TIME-AVERAGING PER MONTH

Time averaging per month can also be a valuable example of the EMF analysis. Using the averaging defined by (6) and (7), monthly filed behavior can be obtained, as shown in Fig. 23, for the year 2022, and in Fig. 24, for the period of 2018-2022.

Fig. 23 shows an increase in the field strength towards the end of the year, which in the micro-environment of S1 can be explained by the necessity and rush of students to complete all their obligations before the end of the year and the upcoming winter break. However, the bounds on $\pm s(m)$ show almost constant dynamics over 2022.

Furthermore, by analyzing the monthly behavior of the E-field per year, some interesting facts can be observed in Fig. 24, such as the sudden drop in the E-field strength in the period March-May 2020 (blue line), highlighted by white rectangle, as unusual detail for this micro-environment. The reason was the closure of the campus during the COVID-19 pandemic when access to the campus and faculties was prohibited. This period was recorded in the E-field, reminding us of this strange EMF event in the micro-environment.

Fig. 24 shows only the E-field curves, while the corresponding standard deviations are presented in Table 8.

TABLE 7. Basic analysis of the E-field and STD over time – for the whole week – 2018-2022.

	2018		2019		2020		2021		2022	
	E [V/m]	STD								
min	0.840	0.085	1.000	0.049	1.073	0.038	1.125	0.064	1.280	0.064
avg	1.065	0.162	1.296	0.149	1.378	0.147	1.558	0.156	1.737	0.179
max	1.330	0.264	1.656	0.320	1.693	0.294	2.006	0.266	2.262	0.354

TABLE 8. Plain analysis of E-field and STD over time – for months – 2018-2022.

	2018		2019		2020		2021		2022	
	E [V/m]	STD								
min	0.817	0.043	1.114	0.049	1.205	0.063	1.417	0.094	1.575	0.088
avg	1.039	0.064	1.282	0.091	1.363	0.085	1.557	0.110	1.783	0.127
max	1.225	0.087	1.452	0.134	1.474	0.133	1.713	0.140	2.022	0.158

FIGURE 23. Averaging over time – per month in 2022.

FIGURE 25. Time averaging vs clustering [55].

FIGURE 24. Averaging over time – per month – 2018-2022.

E. TIME-AVERAGING VERSUS CLUSTERING

The wide-range analyses has been used for EMF data, from those supported by statistics [53], [54], towards trending and seasonality [10], [42], along with clustering, as an interesting way to present results in a simple manner [33] and [34].

Clustering indirectly extracts independent EMF data sets, in which instances have similar or even the same parameters, but differ significantly from other sets. In this context, RF-EMF data obtained from continuous monitoring can be categorized into distinct clusters, providing additional field insight [33].

A recent reference [55] shows that the results of clustering and time averaging are quite informative, regarding the E-field variability and existing dynamics, as shown in Fig. 25.

The clustering from Fig. 25 was based on the Log-Normal Mixture Model (LNMM) [55], where the optimal number of clusters (i.e., the number of components in the distribution) is $K = 4$, regarding RF-EMF data sets for weekdays.

Both approaches follow basic waveform for time averaging per day, presented in Fig. 17; however, by comparing them it can be noticed that while time averaging smooths the RF-EMF data to give a general view about the field behavior, clustering offers a more granular perspective, with richer and even more detailed insights into the data.

The time averaging intentionally simplifies the clusters by reducing (averaging) them to one representative value per set, which is useful for quickly capturing the general

TABLE 9. Time averaging and target groups.

Target group	Field behavior	Peaks	Slopes	Period of high radiation	Dynamics	Variability	Filed levels distribution	Comments
Local community	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		Interested in field behavior per any observed period, as well as period of high radiation, extremes and field dynamics.
General population	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		Interested in field behavior per observed period, as well as period of high radiation, and dynamics.
Laboratories for EMF investigation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Interested in all elements of the field behavior, in relation to their daily work on EMF investigation.
Telecom operators	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Interested in all elements of the field behavior, according to their management of telecom infrastructure and social responsible position.
Agencies for environment protection	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Interested in all elements of the field behavior, regarding their responsibility for the save environment.
EMF decision-makers	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	Interested in usual trends of the field behavior, in relation to their responsibility for allowing installation on new EMF sources.
Scientific community	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Interested in all elements of the field behavior, which serves their scientific research.
EMF standardization bodies	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Interested in all elements of the field behavior, in relation to their work on standardization of methodology for EMF investigation.

behavior of the field. However, it tends to mask the distinct components that may emerge at different times, while, on the other hand, clustering identifies multiple groups within the data, revealing different phenomena in daily changes of RF-EMF [55].

However, comparing the complexity of these approaches, the time averaging comes with a simpler foundation that may be decisive for real-time data processing in EMF monitoring systems, especially in case of annual comparisons of the field behavior, which is not so easy with clustering. Averaging still facilitates the discovery of patterns and behaviors of the field that is quite satisfactory for the general population and their perception of EMF monitoring process and its background.

F. TIME-AVERAGING AND TARGET GROUPS

Using the time-averaging framework, several analyses can be performed for virtually any specified time durations, where the application of the proposed methodology can range from: the elementary need to inform the local community about field behavior per specific periods (day, week, month, year or any other shorter/longer one), as well as comparing field behavior across different locations, as was done in [43] and presented in Fig. 26.

A number of interesting information can be observed in Fig. 26, such as the period of stronger RF-EMF radiation, where the locations of “Suncokret” and “Radosno detinjstvo – Veseli vrtic” kindergartens, as sites with high and medium population density [43], have quite similar duration of this interval for weekdays (11-24 h and 9-24 h), while the elementary school “Vuk Karadzic”, which is in a sparsely populated area [43], and has very short such interval for weekdays, from 10-14 h, matching with the narrow period of the daily shift in school.

FIGURE 26. Comparative EMF evaluation per monitored locations [43].

Many other details can be observed, such as daily or short-term patterns in the field behavior, peaks, slopes, dynamics, variability, levels distribution, etc. [43], each of which may be interesting for specific target group, as presented in Table 9.

Besides all these elements, their annual comparison is one of the major features of time-averaging framework, which is not so easy to be done by a statistical or clustering approach.

The local community is most burdened by the presence of RF-EMF radiation sources [56], especially of concern for the health of children [57]. Thus, information on the behavior of filed over any period, as well as daily periods of high RF-EMF radiation, their extremes and the field dynamics are of great importance for them. The time-averaging framework is able to provide information on all these elements in real time,

together with an annual comparison, so that the community can obtain valid results and establish a rational perception of the local RF-EMF, the corresponding exposure and ultimately the presence of EMF sources in their vicinity.

For the general population, where the residence may not be in the vicinity of any RF-EMF source, all field elements as for the local community are of importance, especially since they may be exposed to EMF at any given point. Thus, the findings of time averaging at sites may serve as a basis for specialized EMF exposure assessment services, such as [58] and [59].

As a major contribution, the time-averaging framework can provide a valuable information for investigation laboratories, in terms of their daily work on EMF testing, where increased entropy on the field is of importance, and especially since the framework provides the usual in situ field behavior, alongside with changes from year to year.

Also, the telecom operators need to demonstrate social responsibility regarding the levels of RF-EMF caused by sources in their wireless network infrastructure. Therefore, objective and transparent information on RF-EMF behavior at the local level is very important for mutual understanding with the community, respecting each other's needs: the community for the EMF save environment and operators for a good quality of the wireless services.

Both the community and operators are in daily contact with the national agencies for environmental protection, in relation with numerous complaints about potential exceeding of EMF safety levels and obligations of agencies to conduct inspection. Thus, these agencies can rely on information from the time-averaging framework, to gain a comprehensive insight into the behavior of in situ RF-EMF, especially over a longer period and its annual trending.

EMF decision-makers are interested in common trends in field behavior, in relation to their responsibility to permit installation on any new EMF sources, at a given location, which may affect both the local community and operators. Thus, the insight into weekly and monthly RF-EMF behavior provided by time averaging can be of particular importance to them, especially in obtaining year-on-year comparisons of the field levels and behavior.

Furthermore, the scientific community is inherently interested in all aspects of EMF, regarding their scientific research on wide-range of EMF topics, including the risk assessment and appropriate communication to the public about EMF [60].

Finally, the national and international standardization bodies may benefit from the time-averaging framework, in relation to standardization of EMF investigation methodologies, as done in [44].

V. CONCLUSION

EMF monitoring systems can provide important insights into variability of EMF at a specific, monitored location or a wider area. Consequently, numerous opportunities may be opened for comprehensive field analyses and for the application of

some additional approaches to RF-EMF time series research, such as the time-averaging framework.

These approaches can reveal hidden details, providing new, valuable insights into the field in the environment, through its dynamics, variability, peaks, slopes and etc. All these elements can be useful for the population's perception of the inevitable presence of EMF in the environment, in the modern, digitally connected world with various wireless telecom services, and ultimately for the effective assessment of EMF exposure.

A time-averaging framework is proposed for the extensive analysis of continuous EMF data in modern EMF monitoring networks, focusing on working at smaller time intervals and analyzing data from periods, such as day, week, month and any other required period. The aim is to estimate typical field behavior in these intervals and later compare them across years.

The framework is illustrated in a case study of EMF data acquired by a sensor in the Serbian EMF RATEL network, installed in a specific EMF micro-environment.

Compared to some other types of RF-EMF analyses, such as those supported by statistics, trending and seasonality, as well as clustering, time-averaging demonstrates a simplicity that may be decisive for real-time data processing in emerging EMF monitoring systems.

Finally, time averaging can generally be applied to any EMF sensor and monitoring network, benefiting a wide audience, from the general population to the professional EMF bodies, opening the potential for further EMF analyses, especially for sensitive areas, such as kindergartens and schools, to reduce public concern about EMF in these micro-environments.

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